

Breaking Rules: Interventions in a Library

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A thesis submitted in conformity with the requirements for the degree of
MA Theatre Making
University of Kent
August 2022

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Acknowledgments

I am deeply grateful to my supervisor, Jayne Thompson. Her scholarly accuracy-made me strive for lucidity at every step of the dissertation process. The careful comments I received on my draughts were matched only by her supervision.

To those artists that allowed me to journey alongside their process and production, I am endlessly indebted. My heartfelt appreciation goes to Sami Belal, Dr. Ali Al-enzi, Salman Al Mutairi, Ahmad Al Mohammedi, Fawaz Al-adwani, and Zainb Al-Wael. You opened the doors to your creative process, offered your insights, and shared your materials with a generosity of spirit that is rare.

My special thanks to my mother, Mariam AL Salem, who believed in me and was beside me throughout my whole life, and my two sisters, Haifa and Wafaa, who responded to my free-floating anxieties with love and humour.

Finally, Rasoul Saghir, the man who had inquired about what I was writing about, came to listen to my papers and said, "This is good, my daughter." He encouraged me to pursue a college degree. He is a rock that I can lean on. More love and passion could not have helped me complete this project. My teacher, thank you.

Abstract

This dissertation is a critical investigation and analysis to a collective of experiments and performance in relation to the theory of spatial rules and explorations of disrupting rules. I examine one ‘rule-bound’ place (the University’s library) to explore and discuss how to disrupt its rules by experimenting with a direct physical engagement with its ‘inhabitants’ (library users). The overall aim of this dissertation is to investigate the relationship between disruptive performance and the rules and behaviours within these places, using a specific site approach to performance through Practice as Research (PaR). Methodologically, to examine the experience of performance that transgresses a place's rules – explicitly to library users during their visit – I conducted four performance-based experiments. In the final, fifth, experiment, I developed an amalgamated approach to disrupting the rules and behaviour in that place by creating a performance. The main objective of this study is to investigate what happens when performances are held within the physical space of communities rather than in theatres explicitly designed for such activities. The innovative approach was to present something unusual in the library through strange performance and eye-catching costumes: by making the audience react and draw their attention or distracting them by something out-of-place despite them being focused on their usual library actions and activities.

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Introduction:

Place is security, space is freedom.

(Yi-Fu Tuan, 1977)

Everywhere you look, you'll find a theatrical element. Theatre has been around for millennia, and the methods used to analyse it have evolved significantly (Freshwater, 2009, p.1). As the action makes its way around the theatre's floor plan, there are, however, many sites where promenade performances can take place. Any places can be a stage; as the English theatre director Brook suggests, "I can take any empty space and call it a bare stage" (Brook, 2008, 1). This is because space denotes the place that we occupy to create or add to. In essence, a place comprises of areas which lie between walls (inner space) or buildings (outer space). When space successfully manifests the emotions, perceptions, and memories of people, we allude to it as a place. As the geographer Tuan said, the relationships between place and space have meaning and merge with the place. The reason is that humans tend to the places where they can express what they want. Therefore, it is also possible to elicit creative theatrical performances in both private and public places (Tuan, 1979, p.61). However, it would be interesting to explore the possibility of unravelling this place and reimagining it in other public places such as cafes, train stations, and most relevant here, libraries. This issue needs careful consideration because relationships are emblematic of people and their places.

The places in a person's world are more than entities that provide the physical stage for life's drama. Some are profound centres of meanings and symbols of experience. As such, they lie at the core of human existence (Buttimer and Seamon, p13)

In this dissertation, I will discuss how to explore the rules of spatial behaviour in ways that disrupt, and behave in ways that enforce rules. As woman from the Middle East, I must follow many rules, behaviours, and laws to conform to society. I am surrounded by many rules that I must follow, regardless of whether I like them or not. As an inquisitive student, I am always curious about the rules and behaviours that bind us in all aspects of our lives. Those who make the rules see things differently, which leads to an imbalance of equality, unfair and unjust interpretations, and implementations of rules to co-exist with. But one must ask, what should one do to follow these rules? Fiona Wilkie's (2002), curiosity led me to find many answers about the place and the rules in place. Taking a curious approach to difficult situations can lead to more creative solutions.

Francesca Gino, a behavioral scientist said:

Studies have found that curiosity is associated with fewer defensive reactions to stress and fewer aggressive reactions to provocation. We also perform better when we're curious (Gino, 2018).

Therefore, this researcher has also become interested in researching the (rules of place) and became more curious about researching how people respond when they see the rules being broken (Wilkie, 2002, p.243). Thus, I selected the library, which has many rules and fixed behaviours. Public libraries have lots of rules that provide guidance on how to behave within a certain place, structure, and environment.

Libraries are organisations that must constantly transform to exist in today's fast-changing world. Libraries also received 96 million website visits in 2014 to 2015—more than three every second. This is a strong base on which to build "(Wilson and Stephens, 2021).

The following chapters are dedicated to a critical explication of some of the attributes of the site that were investigated during the experiments in the Templeman Library. Notably, because it

imposes all of its rules and regulations on us, including the manner in which we interact with everything in the place, this place has the greatest influence in terms of experiences. Therefore, as opposed to being reduced to being just another nebulous component that facilitates the performance, site-related performance is where the site becomes the dominant signifier.

As the case study throughout this dissertation show, the decision to use the library for the site-related performance was partly determined by being given permission, and partly by curiosity about the site. Pearson and McLucas (1981) developed a way of working with sites that uses the terms "host" and "ghost" and "witness" to differentiate between the site itself and any ephemeral architecture that might be built on it. To begin use the term "the host and the ghost", it is important to learn these terms to build a performance in place. For a time, the host site is haunted by a ghost, which created by theatre makers. Succinctly put, the library serves as the host (that is, the site), the work signifies the ghost, whereas the audience would play the role of the witness. This research will involve presenting in a place (the library) with fixed rules and behaviour, disrupting the rules and discussing the results. Links to the video recordings of the experiments that I conducted in the Templeman Library are available in the bibliography .

I. Chapter 1: Relativity of space and rules :

Site-specific theatre:

As stated previously, I am from the Middle East, namely Kuwait. The beginning of Kuwait theatre may be traced back to the beginnings of the school system in 1933, when the first theatrical attempts were made. Faculty and students

would put on a show on special occasions like the Prophet Muhammad's birthday, his pilgrimage, or even just to celebrate Ramadan. The development of Kuwaiti theatre may be divided into two distinct phases: experimentation and improvisation, followed by the founding of the National Theatre in the early 1960s (History of the Theatrical Movement in Kuwait, 2018). However, there has been a delay in the emergence of Arab theatre, the most important of which are factors such as religion, artistic expression, and socialization. As a result, traditional theatre was devoid of diversity. Kuwait has had no prior experience with site-specific performances from that time till now. As a performer, I was inspired to think about how one could use a site other than conventional theatre to create performances in Kuwait because of the abundance of museums, contemporary buildings and places that can be used for this purpose. As a researcher, the goal was to use the Kuwaiti space in a way that will make theatre thrive in the future.

Art resides in the domain of theatre. This domain is notorious for being difficult to describe without either subscribing to self-deprecating admiration or reducing it to art itself. (cf. Geertz 1983:94-5, Bourdieu 1996). Hence the history of the selected site-specific begins with Palaeolithic art related to rituals, ceremonies, and performance, which are the beginning of performances that relate to the place. In ancient Egypt, the Egyptians built temples to the gods and memorialised the pharaohs (Bramwell, Ancient Egypt, 2014). As Schechner argues,

Performance is an inclusive term. Theatre is only one node on a continuum that reaches from the ritualisations of animals (including humans) through performances in everyday life—greetings, displays of emotion, family scenes, professional roles,

and so on—through to play, sports, theatre, dance, ceremonies, rites, and performances of great magnitude (Schechner, 1977, p. 320).

In Greece, rituals were performed, mythical interactions were represented, and festivals were held. Temples were important places of worship for the community. Ancient Greek drama flourished between 550 and 220 BC. The city of Athens was its centre. There are three types of Greek theatre from this period: tragedy, comedy, and satire. (Kowalzig, p.17). From this point, theatre spread to Roman and then Medieval theatres, where plays focused on the representation of Bible stories in churches as well as in architectural, sculptural, and painting styles. (Wickham, p.16). The Renaissance period in Italy, with the emergence of artists such as Leonardo da Vinci and Gian Lorenzo Bernini, as well as the spread of art throughout Europe (Wickham, p.25), had an undeniable impact on site-specific presentations. Then, in the twentieth century, new art forms appeared: modernism, the avant-garde, futurism, and DADA. Dadaism began to reject logic and began to offend "Anti-art," "Anti-War," and other notions that challenged the concept of space and logic (Smith, 2018, p.4). In the early 20th century, theatre started to spread and move to Europe and the United States (Schechner, 1977, p.5). At that time, some artists started painting collages and shifted their focus from the art product to the process. After extended periods of experimentation, they started to create performance places in natural environments that support the development of site-specific performance and contain lots of general ideas and technical models for making performance (rather than formal theatre) by using actual spaces and places rather than theatre halls. As columnist and theatre critic Joyce

MacMillan highlighted, this represented "a move away from designated performance spaces to places with life or history of their own"(MacMillan, 2005, p293).

The development of site-specific performance theatre performed in unexpected sites as a distinct art form was a focus for Mike Pearson during the 1970s and 1980s in the United Kingdom. It was a theatre production that was not performed in a conventional theatre but at a unique, specially adapted location. It might not have been intended to serve any theatrical purposes at all, but these theatre performances give the audience an actual and artistic place to experience – for example, a hotel, courtyard, library, or converted building (Pearson,1997, p.42). In 1981, Pearson established the Brith Gof theatre group, which has staged productions in unusual sites such as the derelict Rover factory in Cardiff for *Gododdin* (1988), the Harland & Wolff shipyard for *Pax* (1990), and the Glasgow and Aberystwyth railway stations for *Pax* (1990). This means moving the site-specific work is, thus, equivalent to destroying it (Serra 1994:194); especially when the performance is staged at the actual site of the performance and is related to the site itself. Some influences on site-specific performance have come from art forms that seem far from performance-based (Smith, 2018, p11). Recently, there have been some artists increasingly interested in the relationship between space, place, and performance.

As a researcher, I have increasingly developed an interest in performances that take place in real spaces within the community rather than in theatres, because I strongly believe site-specific performance can give a holistic experience to an audience in new and memorable ways because of the work's historical reality. Throughout my experiments on site-related performance, I have been fascinated by the ways in which

performance impacts a place, enabling it to tell a variety of stories, and conversely, the intriguing ways in which a place impacts performance. Therefore, the following section will analyse and review the literature that helps to explore the rules of place and behaviour. Site-specific theatre has captivated the imaginations of theatre and fine art practitioners both in the UK and throughout the world. It uses the history, atmosphere, and architecture of a specific place to complement devised or text-based narratives. Fiona Wilkie is one the most influential of the site-specific theatre researchers who written about the Bora Place, which then serves as the foundation for this investigation.

Site-specific and the rules of spatial performance (Fiona Wilkie):

In 2002, *Site-specific performance and the rules of spatial behaviour* included a chapter by Fiona Wilkie. The article surveyed the topic of "site-specific performance and the use of such spaces, which she defined as being subject to a different set of rules" (Wilkie, 2002). In order to describe the "rule bound site," Wilkie developed two related concepts—the "repertoire" and the "inner rule". These ideas resonated with my interest in exploring the space and site for theatre performances rather than conventional theatre, and in particular, working to disrupt the expectations and behaviours of rule-bound sites. The relationship between place, rules, performance, and audience is complex. I was, therefore, confronted with two challenges. The first challenge was focusing on a single goal, which is identifying and choosing *the* place from a number of possibilities – rule-bound sites such as a

shop, a cafeteria, a lecture theatre – and ultimately deciding on the library as the most rule-bound site.

After studying traditional theatre and doing several theatre-based experiments, instead of creating a stage performance, I decided to create a performance based on a non-theatre site. With this research, I hoped that eventually I would break away from the confines of the proscenium. I was looking for an unconventional theatre. Hence, I began searching and thinking about how space can be used to produce a performance and introducing ideas that incorporate the use of space. By interacting with the richness of history and potential sites, I was particularly drawn to the idea of site-related performance. In my view, site-related performances offered people a chance to interact with history and space/place to connect communities and societies around a shared experience. This is what inspires me to gain knowledge because theatre at non-traditional sites in Britain is abundant and presents wonderful performances in different places, and then to transfer this experience to Kuwait.

II. Chapter 2: Experimentation

Libraries :

The word “library,” derived from “book,” (i.e., *liber* – book) is a generic term to describe the formal environment used as the subject space of this research. University libraries are places for reading, studying, and learning, and the culture of their “society” derives from its visitors as well as their readers. There are different types of sites within which and through which performance can be enacted, as well as different kinds of performative relationships within, and through which, sites can

‘temporally manifest’ (Pearson, 2017, p.14). The Templeman Library has numerous rules and regulations that must be followed. As a result of this research, one is able to analyse some library-related studies and experiments. This setting presents an environment which offers site-specific opportunities for research of behaviour.

Performances in libraries have been very successful in Britain. One important piece, in terms of this research is a beautiful show called *The Quiet Volume* by Ant Hampton and Tim Etchells. This piece designed for libraries is a "self-created whisper performance of two people at a time" as part of the London Word Festival. The event took place in the Bishopsgate Institute Library, which has been a forum for debate and the exchange of ideas since the late 1800s. It was decided that participants would be partnered up and given mp3 players. They sit side-by-side at a library table whilst wearing headphones. A voice asks people to listen to the noises surrounding them, the unique music of libraries throughout the world: muted coughs and pages turning. Some books are placed on the table of each person, encouraging them to read. Thus, the act of reading is brought into disrepute. The authors crafted for the audience stories that provoked thought. Sometimes the sound is faint and sometimes it is unpleasant (Etchells and Hampton, 2011). The result is a meditative and joyful experience. The director was clever in encouraging the audience to create their own scenes and in ensuring that the participants thoroughly enjoyed the experience. The concept of this performance was fascinating, and it inspired me to present library experiences in novel and creative ways. Consequently, I began exploring different ways to convey library experiences at Kent’s Templeman Library.

The Templeman Library

This research focuses on performance that goes beyond theatre conventions and disrupts the rules of the place to investigate the subject's expectations of their environment. The choice of place – the library – came after a series of experiments and ideas – finding a place that could be used for research by doing something unfamiliar which might provoke a response from users of the library. The Templeman Library at the University of Kent is a building with collections of books, periodicals, and sometimes recordings are made for the public or members of the institution. The library was contacted to find out what rules and behaviours must be followed. In the library, we must follow several rules and behave appropriately. Principally:

1. It is not acceptable in the library to make excessive noise or act inappropriately.
2. The library's silent study areas are strictly for individual study. You are not allowed to add materials to library items that have been shelved.
3. If you buy a hot drink in the library café and it is not in a secure container, you can only drink it in the library café area on the ground floor.
4. You must take care not to disturb others when eating or drinking, particularly in terms of noise and smell.
5. You are not allowed to drink alcohol in the library, except with permission from the Director of Information Services.
6. We expect you to put your litter and waste liquid in the appropriate bins.

The location's rules are set in stone. The library was one of the most difficult places for me to conduct my experiments. By observing and looking in different areas of the library, I began to explore its potential as a research venue. There was plenty of space

in the library for books, study, student meetings, computers, and exhibitions. I considered where to conduct the experiment, taking into consideration the rules of each space in the library. From this beginning, I became intrigued about how to exploit the environment and circumvent the rules. In addition, as written in *Bora Place* by Wilkie (2002), places where books are made available also have their own unwritten rules, or perhaps permissions:

Why do I feel that I can sit on the floor next to a display in a bookshop but not in, say, a supermarket? Neither place operates a (no sitting) rule, nor do I participate in an implicit agreement with my fellow customers not to sit in these places (Wilkie, 2002,p.249).

It is, thus, useful to talk about some of the categories of rules that affect different places. For example, in the library there are the physical characteristics, rows of books, doors, the main entrance, but there are also implicit rules of behaviour – quiet place, no hot foods –and alongside these are borrowed codes such as fire safety regulations, cooperation to influence behaviour through popular agreement. All these elements that I have listed could be understood as rules. But the question is, are there any rules against sitting on the floor as Wilkie said? What will happen if you break these rules? What will the reaction of the audience be when watching the show? As a result, new ideas and experiments were developed about how to disrupt the place's rules. By utilising a specific approach to i.e., performance through practice, I critically examined the relationship between disruptive performance and the laws and customs that govern these settings (PaR).

Discover the place/space

My first experiment was to investigate the library and its contents. I did this by moving books around, so titles appeared in inappropriate places, for example, biology instead of theatre studies books, and moving them around. I realised that a library has spatial aspects that can communicate the qualities of its areas. This idea came to me after talking to staff members about the items in the library that are not allowed to be used except for the purpose of selecting books, and being reminded that the books are not to be tampered with. To challenge the idea of keeping stock items in their place, I began by shifting books around and experimenting with various body movements, ranging from quick to slow, in the manner of a performance. The aim of the experiment was to study the behaviour of those who were watching and noticing that things were unusual and could cause them to interact; for example, by putting books on the ground and having my audience pass between them. I started by throwing the books to the ground. Wilkie makes the following statement:

Our approach is founded on the principle that movement and communication are essential to the social and economic success of public and private space. That is, the design of space, which determines the movement and interaction of people in the built environment (Wilkie, 2002, p. 256).

My goal, in keeping with Wilkie's approach, was to document my movements and those of my audience. As I placed the books on the floor, I observed the responses of the audience when they saw something unfamiliar. I noticed two students watching me do my work. They were seemed surprised by my behaviour but did not express

anything else to me. Afterward, while discussing their reactions, one of them said that "Seeing the books on the floor made me wonder why they weren't on the bookshelves, and I found that annoying because books should be on the shelves" (Ray, Templeman Library, 2022).

Figure 1 : Books on the Floor, Ram Noureddine, University of Kent, June 15, 2022

The other student said that "the place where you were doing your work was unusual, and I thought it could be interesting to see what was going to happen, so I followed you, and I did not expect you to throw the books." "You were putting some books on the top of the shelves, which is not a place for books, so you are challenging our perspective of the library" (Ram, Templeman Library, 2022). This comment made me rethink why everything should be as it is known to be, according to the rules and expected behaviour. What would happen if the books were not on the shelves?

Apart from what I found out about libraries when using the site, I learned little else from this experiment. However, the students' reactions were crucial. Therefore, I decided to do another experiment with innovative ideas that could produce positive outcomes. To determine whether a response or reaction would occur to witnessing

certain behaviours or breaking rules in an unfamiliar way, I would need to show the students the experiments before I presented them. Although my movements were interesting and "you were breaking the rules to some extent by performing in the library," the dramaturgical feedback from my supervisor was that "there was nothing to suggest that anything radical was occurring: you had been silent, walked up and down the aisles like any other student would, and handled books like any other employee." While the supervisor's comments were correct, I disagreed with her on two counts. As can be seen in the video recording at minute 2:02 ([Experiment 1](#)), the books had been placed on the floor, and the librarian would not have done this. I am not a librarian; therefore, I can rearrange the skillfully placed books while using them. To get satisfactory results, a new experiment had to be developed in response to the criticism and lack of interaction in the first experiment.

Disrupt the rules in the library

The second experiment aimed to find a new site where the audience could interact with me, so I returned to the site of the previous experiment to consider the other options available. In the library, there were large windows outside, so the audience could see the experiment from the outside, which is a great idea since it allows me to access audiences both inside and outside the library. But the difficulty I was experiencing was doing the experiment in its totality, with nobody else to observe and evaluate if the experiment was producing useful results. I had to come up with an idea: hire someone who could look at my experiment and analyse everything from the outside. In this way, I would be able to see the experiment very

clearly. After viewing the library in its entirety, I concluded that the experiment would take place in a tiny room with a view of the entire library, with the audience at the bottom. I made ropes and attached images to them based on stories they would be able to read, and then I pulled the ropes up. But the issue is, did I disrupt the rules of this place? Will the audience read what might have surprised them? The outcomes just were not what I had imagined. As Wilkie mentioned, "the inner rules and the repertoire enable us to consider the complexities of spatial rules and, especially, the ways in which users might engage with these rules" (Wilkie, 2002, p243). Following this, I started reading the established rules again and how to disrupt them. Point by point, I analysed the rules that I could disrupt. After some deliberation, a friend agreed to serve as an external eye and evaluate the work. I began a series of modest experiments involving real concepts. The theatrical performance at the library must be anything but the usual and unusual, otherwise, the exploration and investigation into how to disrupt the rules of the place is meaningless. My supervisor suggested that I try something unusual that might draw attention, which would mark the space as theatrical. Observing the reactions of an individual audience is the best way to conduct accurate experiments. People's experiences can immediately provoke action in others, so that they interact. The purpose of this experiment was to bring the experience back in a new form. Researchers change one variable at a time in academic experiments so that they can determine what caused the outcome. My questionnaire studies were done in front of an audience. A questionnaire was provided in order to interact with the audience who watched the experiment. The following questions were asked: Was it difficult for you to understand what I did in

this experiment? How was the atmosphere overall ? Do you see any disruptive rules in the space? They reported that they saw the rules of the place being broken, but nothing surprised them except that they saw an actor moving around a narrow space while she was between the shelves, as shown in the video ([Experiment 2](#)), with simple movements and moving between the books. The inquiry seemed to unsettle the audience. They began to observe my actions: whether they understood what I was doing or whether they thought I was infringing the space's rules was unclear. They were not aware of the outcome, so I needed to improve my experiment.

Creating a performance

There were lots of behaviours and rules that should have been followed. To find a suitable way to perform the experiment, I began to observe the position of the shelves, books, and participants. After careful consideration, I decided that the experiment would be a journey through the library, wandering from one location to another so that the library's visitors could observe me. The goal of this experiment was for me to acquire develop my experiments further and integrate new ideas. I created a story focused on the challenges faced by Middle Eastern women to fit in with a culture and how they can adapt to a society full of rules and regulations that make them unsuitable. As Kaye has mentioned, "to present the place, is, in this sense, and analogously to its practice, to construct a removal from it " (Kaye,2013, p.7) – in other words, to exist within but also apart from the rules of place. Thus, the library is a society with rules, behaviour, and regulations, and that is where the idea for the performance came from, and the performer is the woman who tries to be different in

every aspect of her life. The first thing she did was picket in the middle of the library, denouncing all the nation's rules and behaviour. Wearing a white outfit, as you can see in this video ([Experiment : 3](#)) , she travels from one area to another across cultures, and everyone looks at her differently. She wants to be the white rose that spreads roses in performance she travels, but she loses acceptance, and at the conclusion of the play, she suddenly appears in black clothing, collapses, and dies. The show's concept is based on one of the women's books called *Feminism, Interrupted* by (Sydney Calkin, 2015) that has already begun to rise in our society of discrimination and racism. It was a successful step in attracting everyone's attention because the library is a place for reading and drafting books. The initial aim was to capture the viewer's attention. We learn that literature can have different meanings and interpretations because it is a tool to reflect the ideals of our society. After I concluded my experiment, I walked to the audience to seek their opinions on what they saw, and one of the viewers responded: "I liked what you did because you disrupted us in a positive way." Another stated, "I was focused on my writing when I sensed someone walking and capturing my attention, so when I turned, I was surprised. Was it a play, a wedding, or an advertisement? Those were my thoughts". With these reactions, I was able to reflect more on the last experiment in which I broke the rules of the place with a short performance based on my previous experiment.

Shaping the performance:

In this performance, I learned many things from the last three experiments; creating something new requires lots of work, different attempts, and learning. I changed everything from my last experiments, such as places, accessories, and ideas. The immediate reaction I most often get when recommending changing two or more factors simultaneously in the rules method is : "How will I know which factor caused the change in response?" As I started to analyse and arrange ideas, I found out what worked and what failed in my previous experiences. I began at the library or at the site and sequentially organised my ideas. According to Pearson:

Site can be directly related to the story's topic, theme, or structure, but it will always be clear as context, framing, or subtext (Pearson, 2007c).

I was doing my experiments in areas that were narrow and utterly isolated from vision, unless someone decided to search for a specific book that could be present in this area. Consequently, my experiment was not seen by the audience who were in the library. I found no practical results when I tried to leave the books and disrupt the rules by walking fast. I invited a specific audience, and the reactions from the audience were that they saw an event in the library. Still, it did not attract any attention that I was disrupting any of the library rules. After several experiments, the picture gradually became more precise , and here I decided the first thing was to look for someone who could help me in my experiment , because it would observe for me. Next, I chose a clear place where everyone could see me. Then I thought about how to attract their attention in a strange way while breaking the rules of the place. Experiments always take a lot of time and require more patience, but during the period I was thinking of

developing my idea, my supervisor followed up with me on four experiments and encouraged me to develop new ideas every time. My last experiment was meaningful. I created a storyline about 'Flower', who left the book and started to discover the new place that they forced her to be. She cannot live in this place because she does not belong here, so she tries to break the rules of the space by moving things and playing with the books. There was no interaction, so she died there. The result of this experience was that everyone broke the rules without feeling the disruption was negative because of the meaning of the story that guided everyone to follow with interest.

Not all experiments result in optimization. Learning which elements had an impact, and how much, is often all that is required. The paper that was put on the white skirt attracted criticism. It was clear that it was printed and pasted, and it did not have an attractive appearance, as you can see below :

Figure 2 : Stick papers on the skirt, Ram Noureddine, University of Kent, July 6, 2022

When my supervisor directed me to demonstrate something strange and unfamiliar, I used a structured approach that gave the experiment a major twist. The use of costumes enabled me to develop the experiment in a new and innovative way and , of course,

allowed me to improve the idea by building on previous projects and continuing the improvement process later if necessary .

Performance (Flower):

In response to the latest reactions and suggestions from my supervisor, I decided to present the final performance. The last experiment was good, but it lacked some arrangements that could have improved everything. Indeed, I started planning for the final show, which would be in the library. I made a map of the path and time that the show will be on, which would allow the audience to follow and know exactly where the show is to be presented. Identifying the place is very important for the viewer and for the artist, as it is the meeting place in case the performances are in various places or are transferred from one place to another. According to Tuan,

The experience of space and time is largely subconscious. We have a sense of space because we can move and of time because, as biological beings, we undergo recurrent phases of tension and ease (Tuan, 1979, p118) .

When presenting the performance and moving from one place to another, the idea of persistence must also be considered, which was successful in my last experiment, which helped the audience to observe what might happen. The idea of the performance called "Flower" is in accordance with the previous idea, with some modifications that I need. In the previous experiment, I used the white crinoline and put some papers on it, as shown below:

Figure 3 : Add more papers to the skirt, Ram Noureddine, University of Kent, July 24, 2022

On the white crinoline, I placed some newspapers and coloured papers to make it look attractive. After that, I made a ‘map’, of the show from the moment of entering the library to the end, so that it would be easier for the audience to follow the show smoothly and not lose scenes as you can see below:

Figure 4: The Map, Templeman Library University of Kent, July 24, 2022

The performance called (Flower): is an oriental woman living in a community with traditional social norms and discrimination/abuses against women that result in stigmatisation and traumatization, preventing girls and young women from gaining the education they desire, participating in society, having a voice, and accessing opportunities. According to Granati:

Today, 1 in 3 women experience violence in their lifetime; 830 women die every day from preventable pregnancy-related causes; only 1 in 4 parliamentarians worldwide are women; and it will be 2086 before we close the gender pay gap if present trends

continue with no action. Gender inequality is rife. As the international community unites around the Sustainable Development Agenda, we owe it to the next generations to strive for a world where women have voice, choice, and agency and enjoy the same rights as men (Granati, 2000).

The flower was living in a book when someone took her to the Templeman Library from the Middle East. She lived in a book when someone took her to the Templeman library from the Middle East. She came out of the book trying, and the show began, as shown in the picture below.

Figure 5: First scene of the performance, Ram Noureddine, University of Kent, July 25, 2022

She tried adapting to the new place down smack in the middle of the library, giving everyone a good guess as to what she was up to. What kind of self-expression does this woman seek to achieve? Despite her best efforts, she just could not get used to her new surroundings since she always had the unsettling feeling that she was an outsider. She wears a white dress as she walks from one section of the library to another. As a result of her history, her skirt is covered in pieces of paper. In despite of her best efforts, it all seems to stick to her as she attempts to let go. There are books on the ground to her right and left as she walks. The illustrations on the booklets depict horribly distorted women as you can see in the picture below

Figure 6: Hold the dreadful book, Ram Noureddine, University of Kent, July 25, 2022

She drops a volume on the floor and spins around to face the library's gloomy wall. The library's one and only black wall. The café's wall was here, but it was locked. As you can see in this video at 7:34 min ([Performance](#)). Suddenly, she fled to a wall, where she discovered even more posters depicting impoverished women. When someone asked, "Are you OK?" she had already begun ripping apart artwork. Since she does not comprehend his language, she is at a lack of words. She said in her language: "لم أفهم" meaning in English (I don't understand). Then he said, "Excuse me?" She is running to her place at the beginning and going back inside the book. Many of the things Wilkie said were possible, I sought out to include in this performance without ever once checking with anyone to see if it was impossible. The regulations do not explicitly prohibit running in the library, but we follow a standard of sequential behaviour and do not break the mould. People everywhere tend to act in the same ways as those around them. I had to disrupt the rules and behaviour of the library in a variety of ways to sit in the middle of the library, which caused a few library patrons to observe in amazement. Everything I did was against the library's rules. For

example, it can be obligate as a creative strategy that was executed to show something uncommon in the library using an odd presentation and attention-grabbing costumes. It will get the audience's attention to react while they were otherwise preoccupied with routine library activities. To conclude, it could be said; What was missing from the performance was the audience, who would have enhanced the performance had they been present and the performance, as well as the experiments that were previously presented.

III. Chapter 3: Challenges the rules of the Space/Place

Exploring and interrogating performance:

There were many difficulties that I encountered during my experiments. This was one of the most important reasons for me to revise and clarify the ideas of that I was developing. As I struggled with writing a text for a specific place or site, such as a library, I also faced trouble directing ideas. As Smith highlighted:

There is an ambiguity that persists about the status of any playwright who write for, in, about or around non-theatre-designated sites. There is a sense that, for writers at least, this writing is either novelty or “hack “work, distraction from the real business of writing for “the stage” which is the generator /distributor of single texts to multiple venues. (Smith, 2018, p. 178)

Therefore, structural analysis and dramatic criticism helped me a lot in building ideas and setting a clear map for the performance in the place. It was not easy to perform a show in a place because of the difficulty of controlling the place during experiments or exercises. One of the most important things I learned is how to know the identity of

the place and work with it according to what is available. With each experiment, I discovered something new through different ways, some of which changed the site of the show, or developed the performance, or the interaction and critical response of the audience. I believe that the presence of the audience in the venue is essential for interacting with the theatrical performance and tracking the audience's reactions. During my experiments, I encountered a major obstacle in that the Templeman Library was devoid of visitors and students due to the July presentation of my experiments; however, there were a few that followed, and I was able to record the audience's responses. I will give more details on the importance of the audience's presence all through performances at this place.

1. Library communities and audience behavior:

Individuals' behaviour in various situations reveals various aspects of themselves. A person's behaviour around friends is not the same as their behaviour around teachers, strangers, or parents. According to Goffman, these are the new roles played in another scene in a new setting, which reflect many circumstances at various phases in people's lives. Role performance refers to the adaptation of behaviours to non-identical contexts (Shamus, 2020). The communities are those who instil appropriate social behaviour through social upbringing, and those who integrate cultural heritage into their daily practices of customs and traditions after believing in and accepting them until they become part of their personality. While the artists perform their performances in the sites of the communities, the people are always gathered in their gathering places. I experienced this when I was in the library where

there is a dedicated group for them that meets for reading, studying, and in-depth discussions. There are special rules in the library that control how people behave in terms of respecting the rights of others and desiring peace so that everyone may focus on whatever they want.

The affordance of certain sites and of certain unfolding performance practice offer you the possibility of characterising your audience giving them functions, of recruiting them into the site and the actioner fiction, of engaging their bodies as shape, supports, backdrops, of engaging their imagination and creativity in improvised actions, world making, of involving them as citizens and decision makers in relational performance (Smith, 2018, p193).

The audience is a group of people from various roles in the theatre industry that they like. People watching a performance and responding on their behaviour by laughing, applauding, and many more who come together to watch a performance. Society is changing according to place, and so, consequently, the self has been renewed. Humans react to what they see and imagine who is offering to appear around others.

2. The outcome of deconstructing special rules

During multiple experiments in the library to disrupt the rules and behaviour of the site in devising ways to break the rules and stage theatrical performances in the place, several questions were asked, including how good is the performance while breaking the rules of the venue? How was the presentation communicated to the audience? And what are the challenges faced in all these experiments, and were there positive results or no results?. I'll start first in the place which is the primary pulse of

the experiences being the most important component. Experiments in places are not easy because the place limits and imposes itself on the artist and the audience, so the artists must be compatible with the challenges of the place. I see and think of closely related processes. According to Tuan:

I see means I understand. Seeing, it has long been recognized, is not a simple recording of light stimuli; it is a selective and creative process in which environment stimuli are organized into flowing structures that provide signs meaningful to the purposive organism (Tuan,1979, p10).

There are new forms of stable sites within and through which performance may be performed, as well as new kinds of performative relationships within and through which sites can temporally manifest. My choice of place in my first and second experiences was based on the basics of how to break the rules of place through books. One of the most important conditions and controls that have been set for the place is that the books on the shelves should not be used except in the case of borrowing. No satisfactory result was found through which the concept of breaking the rules of place and behaviour was deduced. But with the continuation of providing experiments, the idea began to mature with increased clarity. As part of my documenting and analysis process, and my research into the various people and influences in the Templeman Library, was the best experiment on which I relied in terms of disrupting the rules of place, behaviour, and audience interaction in the library, which led to the development of the theory of using the dramaturg, specific place, and audience interaction.

IV. Conclusion

Finally, I feel it is important to stress the significance of performances in a place for their liveliness and direct interaction with the audience, as well as communication with the site's contents. The live experiences in the place have opened doors and ideas for me about how to produce performances, especially in the place and in a completely different way than giving a theatrical performance in a traditional theater. Which creates innovations of ideas and many ways that follow to present a performance in a special place. Specifically, the experiences presented in the library and the difficulty of the place. As Wilkie mentioned,

The performance that locates itself in an everyday setting in inviting others to experience its effects through a large and complex frame. For Mike Pearson, site specific performance (Wilkie, 2002, p258)

Through library-based experiments and their performance outcomes, I explored ways to break the rules and amaze the audience with something unexpected that improves the aesthetic meaning and importance of the work. My focus has been on how I will refer to as the anticipation of behavioural traditions and rules, what can be done and observed in place, and how to navigate it. And I sought something unexpected, as well as what to do in an unexpected manner that disrupts the rules and norms of the location. As stated by Hamilton, "Curiosity, by recognising contradictory information, can assist individuals in coping, dealing with unwelcome emotions, and having to accept conflict" (Hamilton, 2019). As part of my research on behaviour, I examine the responses of viewers in the library and the audience watching a show. I produced the

idea of using only my natural inquisitiveness to identify the reasons why we should not explore and the reasons for creating the library's rules of conduct by experimenting with all applicable rules and analysing them further to find the obvious. As I present my first experiment on site, my reading of specific site theatre and the ways to perform it, was instrumental in developing my skills in using the location. I do not deny that it is more challenging than presenting performances in a theatre, because the theatre can be configured however it pleases, whereas the presentation of the place is fixed, and you must use the tools and vocabulary of the place to adapt your abilities and knowledge to adapt my future-focused ideas and experiences in this space. The performance that places itself in an ordinary environment extends an invitation to others to experience the effects of its actions within a broad and intricate framework. The occurrence and the effects are interconnected with both components in a temporal, spatial, physical, and psychological way. For Pearson, site-specific performances

Are extremely generative of signs: the multiple meanings and readings of activity and site intermingle, amending and compromising one another. (Pearson,1997, p.96)

The site remains the same, but the method of presenting the theatrical performance must be elaborated upon and thoroughly researched to discover multiple methods for presenting impressive performances in the future. But the effects are not limited to the site of activity but also present themselves in re-thinking, remembering, and performing aspects of this specific performance for others.

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